

Production Efficiency Analysis Overburden on Activities Backfilling Reclamation using Simplex Method at PT. Lamindo Inter Multikon Site Bunyu Island, North Kalimantan

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Abstract:- Reclamation is one of the activities that must be carried out in mining operations. One of the reclamation activities is the closure of ex-mining holes (voids). Not all of these former mining holes (voids) can be closed. However, the effort that can be made by mining business actors is to close voids which can still be closed to minimize the amount of waste, namely acid mine drainage which is accommodated in the mining area. Carrying out reclamation and post-mining activities requires costs. However, this can be minimized by using the right methods and designs. One of these methods is backfilling which has the advantage of setting distances or distances that can be adjusted. Meanwhile, the calculation of the use of tools can be calculated using the simplex method with minimization. This research was conducted at PT. Lamindo Inter Multikon located on Bunyu Island, Bunyu District, Bulungan Regency, North Kalimantan. In this study the results obtained in area 1 a target of 220,000 Bcm can be achieved if using 7 tools. This is in accordance with manual calculations which obtained the number 6.82 and in the POM software through iterative calculations obtained the number 7.26. In area 2 the target of 205,000 Bcm can be achieved using 6 tools. This is in accordance with manual calculations which obtained the number 6.35 and through the POM software through iterative calculations obtained the number 6.142

Keywords: Reclamation, Backfilling, Simplex Method.

I. INTRODUCTION

Coal is organic sedimentary fuel solid hydrocarbons formed from plants that have undergone biochemical, chemical and physical decay in oxygen free conditions that take place at certain pressures and temperatures over a very long period of time.

Coal mining activities using heavy equipment result in decrease in soil productivity, soil compaction, erosion and sedimentation. In post mining land, the pH of soil becomes very acid due to heavy metal contamination. These extreme conditions can be overcome by improving soil conditions, namely liming or adding organic matter,

improving the drainage system to prevent waterlogging and watering. As well as selecting the right tree species that can adapt to these extreme conditions. Restoration of ex-mining land by applying organic and inorganic fertilizers can improve the chemical, physical and biological properties of the soil on land that has been disturbed by mining activities so that it is suitable and useful for revegetation activities.

Reclamation activities are carried out aiming to restore the function of the land and manage quality environment post mines generally have acid and nutrient poor soil, so effort are made to increase soil fertility by means of fertilization. Nutrient status in the soil is always changing, depending on the season, soil management and plant species.

The process of reclamation activities carried out mechanically causes environmental pollution in the form of soil and water pollution. Soil management on post mining land provides great benefits for the growth of flora and fauna disturbed by mining activities. Organic and inorganic fertilizers are expected to improve soil conditions and support plant growth in an effort to increase reclamation success. Fertilization is generally interpreted as adding plant nutrients to the soil.

Post land mining coal generally arid, vegetation is difficult to grow and becomes unproductive. When it rains, it is difficult for water to seep into the ground or most of it flows on the surface, as a result groundwater is reduced and erosion continues to increase, even though the threat of flooding and landslides continues to lurk. It is unfortunate if post coal mining land eventually becomes unproductive and actually brings disaster to humans. By therefore, post mining land should not be abandoned and serious efforts are needed to restore the conditions of the land to normal or at least close to its pre-mining state. Recovery efforts to restore post mining land conditions are called reclamation.

➤ *In Carrying Out Reclamation Activites, A Concept of the Stage must be made, Namely:*

- *Surveying Stage*

At this stage topography data is collected to determine the volume of overburden which will be transferred to the landfill of ex-mining pits.

- *Mine Planning Stage*

This stage is the most important stage because it is in the process mine planning will affect the level of efficiency in production, where the determination of heavy equipment used will greatly affect cost company. At this stage the creation of the concept is carried out by making design from loading point until dump area, spacing, manufacture safety plan, calculation of heavy equipment to be used and calculation of estimated loss time in production

- *Data Processing Stage*

At this stage the existing data is processed using some software. For data processing design mine use mine craft software5.7, the calculation of volume and production

progress rate on a weekly basis using surpac software, and cost calculations and determination calculations matching fleet using excel.

As for this research calculate work compatibility match factor) loading and conveying equipment, calculating the optimal production resulting from the stripping activity over burden based on Linear Programming Simplex method, calculating the optimal means of conveyance in production over burden based on the Simplex method, and calculate the minimum production costs that can be generated on production overburden based on the simplex method.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW & RESEARCH AREAS

➤ *Company Location*

The location of this research area is in the Bunyu Island coal mine, Bulungan Regency, North Kalimantan Province which can be shown at the coordinate points of WIUP PT. Lamindo Inter Multikon.

Fig 1 Location Map PT. LIM

➤ *Research Area Stratigraphy*

The rock formations that make up the area research which consists of sandy clay, sandstone with coal inserts. The constituent sandstones are quartz sandstone, sandstone containing coal chips and sandstone with a layered layer structure from the distribution of rock types, it can be shown that the depositional process was in the delta and shallow

sea areas. The rock formations that make up the study area consist of sandy claystone, sandstone with coal inserts. The constituent sandstones are quartz sandstone, sandstone containing coal chips and sandstone with a layered layer structure from the distribution of rock types, it can be shown that the depositional process was in the delta and shallow sea areas.

Table 1 Regional Statistics WIUP PT. LIM

TIME	ERA PERIOD	EPOCH		FORMATION		
KENOZOIKUM	Kuartar	Holosen		Aluvium		
		Pleitosen	End	Sajau	Sinjin	
			Mid			
			Begining			
	Tertiary	Pleitosen		Tabul	Jelai	
		Miosen	End	Meliat		
			Mid			
			Begining			
		Olisogen		Naintipo		
		Eosen		Sembakun		
		Paleosen		Bengarea		
	Chalk	End				
		Lower				

➤ *Regional Geology*

Based on the lithological characteristics, the rocks deposited at PT. Lamindo Inter Multikon are grouped into several formations, namely:

- Alluvium Formation, composed of mud, silt, sand, gravel and oral lithologies which are beach, river and swamp sediments.
- The Sajau Formation, composed of quartz sandstone, claystone, siltstone, coal, lignite and conglomerate, layers of planar cross-sectional sediments and bowls, bioturbation, parallel waters, iron nodules and fossil wood.
- The Tabul Formation, composed of cross lithology of claystone, mudstone, sandstone, limestone and coal at the top, the age of this formation is late Miocene.
- Meliat Formation, composed of crosses of sandstone, claystone and shale with coal inserts, having a layered layer structure, bioturbation and containing limestone nodules, this formation is of middle Miocene age and deposits in shallow marine circles.
- The Naintipo Formation, olisogenous and early Miocene in age, is composed of cross- marl lithology, conglomerate rock, planar and cross-bedding sedimentary layer bowls, bioturbation, parallel waters, iron nodules and fossil wood.
- The Sinjin Formation, composed by cross lithology, this formation is Pleitocene in age.
- The Sembakun Formation, deposited unconformably above the lake formation, has a middle Eocene age. At the bottom, this formation consists of red sandstone and

conglomerate. At the top consists of carbon-rich mudstone.

➤ *Calculation of Productivity*

In this study the productivity calculations obtained at PT. Lamindo Inter Multikon are as follows:

- *Tool Work Compatibility (Match Factor)*

Tool work compatibility done using Equation (1). The data used in the process of calculating the work compatibility of the tool is data cycle time, the number of loading and hauling equipment. From the calculations that have been done, the following data is obtained:

$$MF = \frac{n \times Na \times Ctm}{Nm \times Cta} \quad (1)$$

Information:

- MF = Match Factor
- N = Lots of charging
- Na = Number of means conveyance
- Nm = Number of means of loading
- Ctm = Cycle Time loading tools
- Cta = Cycle time conveyance

From these data and equations, it is obtained that the work compatibility of each tool is 1.21 ; 1,4 ; 1.5. With matching factor(MF) obtained from each unit > 1, it can be concluded that the loading equipment has worked 100% but the transportation equipment has worked <100% so that: there is a waiting time for the transportation equipment.

Table 2 Data Produktifitas Alat Muat

Unit Excavator	Waktu Tersedia (T)	Waktu Kerja Efektif (W)	Waktu Breakdown (R)	Waktu Standby
Doosan 520LCV (EX-01)	720 Hours/Mounth	471,9 Hours/Mounth	109,1 Hours/Mounth	139 Hours/Mounth
Doosan 520LCV (EX-02)	720 Hours/Mounth	471,9 Hours/Mounth	109,1 Hours/Mounth	139 Hours/Mounth

• *The Effectiveness of Loading and Conveying Equipment*
 To get the Effectiveness of Loading and Conveyance equipment, it is carried out using equations (2) to (5) and the input data can be seen in Table 3.

$$MA = \frac{W}{W+R} \times 100\% \quad (2)$$

$$PA = \frac{W+S}{W+R+S} \times 100\% \quad (3)$$

$$UA = \frac{W}{W+S} \times 100\% \quad (4)$$

$$EU = \frac{W}{W+R+S} \times 100\% \quad (5)$$

Information:

R = Time maintenance heavy equipment

S = Time standby heavy equipment

W = Tool working time

The effectiveness obtained in this OB Removal activity can be seen from table 5 & table 6.

Table 3 Effectiveness of Load Tool

Unit Excavator	PA (%)	MA (%)	UA (%)	EU (%)
DX 520LCV (PC01)	88%	77%	97%	58%
DX 520 LCV (PC02)	88%	78%	95%	58%

Table 4 The Effectiveness of Conveyance

Unit Dumptruck	PA (%)	MA (%)	UA (%)	EU (%)
DA01 (ADT01)	88%	84%	92%	58%
DA 02 (ADT02)	87%	88%	86%	58%
DA 03 (ADT03)	87%	89%	87%	58%
DA 04 (ADT04)	88%	82%	77%	58%
DA 05 (ADT05)	85%	88%	90%	58%
DA 06 (ADT06)	84%	91%	80%	58%
DA 07 (ADT07)	88%	84%	81%	58%
DA 08 (ADT08)	89%	87%	83%	58%
DA 09 (ADT09)	84%	80%	89%	58%
DA 10 (ADT10)	85%	86%	90%	58%
DA 11 (ADT11)	85%	85%	79%	58%
DA 12 (ADT12)	86%	85%	83%	58%
DA14 (ADT14)	83%	83%	83%	58%

Productivity of Transportation & Loading equipment to find the percentage value of the productivity of a tool, you can use equation (6) for loading equipment & (7) for transportation equipment, namely:

$$Q = \frac{Kb \times Eff \times 3600}{ct} \quad (6)$$

$$Q = \frac{n \times Kb \times Eff \times 3600}{ct} \quad (7)$$

➤ *Case Studies*

open pit mining project (open PIT) PT.Lamindo Inter Multikon will carry out a reclamation activity. It can be seen that reclamation activities are very calculated cost/ cost. From several methods can be determined method backfilling is a very efficient method that can be used in the closure of ex-mining holes (voids). This is because the distance

(distance) which can be set accordingly planning design. The following is known reclamation project data below:

- OB volume target in area 1 = 220.000 Bcm/ Mounth
- OB volume target in area 2 = 205.000 Bcm/ Mounth
- Dumping distance area 1 = 400 m
- Dumping distance 2 = 500 m
- Average production 1 hour/dt = 84 Bcm
- Transport capacity hauler = 14 Bcm
- Available Work Hours = 15,73/day

If some of these data are known, then here the author determines the level of production efficiency in areas 1 & 2 by calculating the use of tools (match fleet) using the simplex method.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

➤ Area 1 Strategy Calculations

Fig 2 Opening Software POM

Objective		Instruction						
☐ Maximize		There are more results available in additional windows. These ma						
☒ Minimize								
Cj	Basic Variables	1	1	0	0	0	0	Quantity
		X1	X2	artfcl 1	surplus 1	artfcl 2	surplus 2	
Phase 1 - Iteration 1								
1	artfcl 1	26	0	1	-1	0	0	189
1	artfcl 2	0	26	0	0	1	-1	189
	zj	-26	-26	1	1	1	1	378
	cj-zj	26	26	0	-1	0	-1	

Fig 3 Completion of Iteration 1 Area 1

Iteration 2								
0	X1	1	0	0,0385	-0,0385	0	0	7,2692
1	artfcl 2	0	26	0	0	1	-1	189
	zj	0	-26	2	0	1	1	189
	cj-zj	0	26	-1	0	0	-1	

Fig 4 Completion of Iteration 2 Area 1

Iteration 3								
0	X1	1	0	0,0385	-0,0385	0	0	7,2692
0	X2	0	1	0	0	0,0385	-0,0385	7,2692
	zj	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
	cj-zj	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	

Fig 5 Completion of Iteration 3 Area 1

Phase 2								
1	X1	1	0	0,0385	-0,0385	0	0	7,2692
1	X2	0	1	0	0	0,0385	-0,0385	7,2692
	zj	1	1	-0,0385	0,0385	-0,0385	0,0385	14,5385
	cj-zj	0	0	0,0385	-0,0385	0,0385	-0,0385	

Fig 6 Final Output Phase Area 1

From these calculations, for area 1 use hauler as many as 7 units. If proven by manual calculation, the calculation is as follows:

• Area 1

Target = 220.000 Bcm/ Mounth (Actual/effective working days 24 days) So;

Target be achieved in 1 day if actual time 16 work hours:

$$\frac{220.000}{24} = 9.666,67 \text{ Bcm/day}$$

Hourly Target:

$$\frac{9.166,67}{16} = 573 \text{ Bcm/Hours}$$

Calculations of the use tools:

$$\frac{\text{Target per jam}}{\text{BCM/DT}} = \frac{573}{84} = 6,82$$

From these calculations, for area 1 use hauler as many as 7 units. This is the same as the results of calculations using simplex era.

➤ Area 2 Strategy Calculations

Objective		Instruction						
☐ Maximize		There are more results available in additional windows. These ma						
☒ Minimize								
Iterasi Area 2 Jurnal Peny								
Cj	Basic Variables	1	1	0	0	0	0	Quantity
		X1	X2	artfcl 1	surplus 1	artfcl 2	surplus 2	
Phase 1 - Iteration 1								
1	artfcl 1	28	0	1	-1	0	0	172
1	artfcl 2	0	28	0	0	1	-1	172
	zj	-28	-28	1	1	1	1	344
	cj-zj	28	28	0	-1	0	-1	

Fig 7 Completion of Iteration 1 Area 2

Iteration 2								
0	X1	1	0	0,0357	-0,0357	0	0	6,1429
1	artfcl/2	0	28	0	0	1	-1	172
	zj	0	-28	2	0	1	1	172
	ci-zj	0	28	-1	0	0	-1	

Fig 8 Completion of Iteration 2 Area 2

Iteration 3								
0	X1	1	0	0,0357	-0,0357	0	0	6,1429
0	X2	0	1	0	0	0,0357	-0,0357	6,1429
	zj	0	0	2	0	2	0	0
	ci-zj	0	0	-1	0	-1	0	

Fig 9 Completion of Iteration 3 Area 2

Phase 2								
1	X1	1	0	0,0357	-0,0357	0	0	6,1429
1	X2	0	1	0	0	0,0357	-0,0357	6,1429
	zj	1	1	-0,0357	0,0357	-0,0357	0,0357	12,2857
	ci-zj	0	0	0,0357	-0,0357	0,0357	-0,0357	

Fig 10 Final Output Phase Area 2

From the stages of completion above it can be determined that for area 2 usedumptruckas many as 6 units. If proven by manual calculation, the calculation is as follows:

• Area 2

Target = 205.000 Bcm/ Mounth (Actual/effective working days 24 days) So;

Target be achieved in 1 day if actual time 16 work hours :

$$\frac{205.000}{24} = 8.541,67 \text{ Bcm/day}$$

Hourly Target:

$$\frac{8.541,67}{16} = 534 \text{ Bcm/Hours}$$

Calculations of the use tools:

$$\frac{\text{Target perjam}}{\text{BCM/DT}} = \frac{534}{84} = 6,35$$

From these calculations, for area 2 use dump truckas many as 6 units. This is the same as the results of calculations using simplex iterations.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

➤ Conclusions

From the analysis that has been done by the author, it can be concluded that:

- In area 1 the target of 220,000 Bcm can be achieved if you use 7 tools. This is in accordance with manual calculations obtained at 6.82 and on software POM through iteration calculations obtained the number 7.26.
- In area 2 the target of 205,000 Bcm can be achieved if you use 6 tools. This is in accordance with manual calculations obtained by 6.35 and through software POM via Iteration calculations get the number 6.142

➤ Suggestions

From the research that has been done, there are several suggestions from the author, as follows:

- Preferably a review is needed, if discussing the issue of production efficiency then the mine design must be analyzed
- We recommend that you need to add several parameters in planning production activities, namely safety factor& safety plan according to the procedure in force. This can be described in the mine planning design.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Jay Heizer, and Barry Render. 2006. Operations Management. Terjemahan Dwi anoegrah wati dan Alhamdy, Indra. Jakarta. Salemba Empat.
- [2]. Assauri, S. (2008). Manajemen Produksi dan Operasi edisi revisi. Jakarta: Lembaga Penerbit Fakultas Ekonomi Universitas Indonesia.
- [3]. Herjanto, E. (2009). Sains manajemen. Grasindo.
- [4]. Handoko, T. H. (1984). Dasar-dasar manajemen produksi dan operasi. BPFE.
- [5]. Soekartawi.(1995). AnalisisUsahatani. Universitas Indonesia..
- [6]. Adinda, A., & Yulhendra, D. (2020). Studi Optimasi Produktivitas Alat Gali Muat dan Alat Angkut Menggunakan Metode Linear Programming Pada Perolehan Produksi Overburden PT. Surya Global Makmur Jobsite Pemusiran, Kabupaten Sarolangun, Provinsi Jambi. *Bina Tambang*, 5(2), 238-249.
- [7]. Bascetin, A. & Ercelebi, S. G. (2009). Optimization of Shovel-Truck System for Surface Mining. *Journal of The Southern African Institute of Mining & Metallurgy*. 109. 433-439.

- [8]. Burt, C. (2008). An Optimisation Approach to Materials Handling in Surface Mines. Thesis. Department of Mathematics and Statistics. Curtin University of Technology.
- [9]. Cacceta, L & Burt, C. (2013). Equipment Selection for Surface Mining : A Review. *Journal Interface*. 44 (2): 143-162.
- [10]. Christian, Sugiarto. (2013). Penerapan Linear Programming Untuk Mengoptimalkan Jumlah Produksi Dalam Memperoleh Keuntungan Maksimal Pada Cv Cipta Unggul Pratama. *Journal The WINNERS*. 14(1): 55-60.
- [11]. Franik, Ewa & Franik, Tadeusz. (2009). Application of Non Linear Programming for Optimizatoin of Factors of Production in Mining Industry. Alcon Pharmaceutical Ltd anovartis Company. Fribourg.
- [12]. Ismail, Hijir. (2018). Sebuah Formulasi Permasalahan Optimalisasi Produksi Tambang Galian Marmer. *Jurnal Matematika, Statistik dan Komputasi*. 14 (2): 187-191.
- [13]. Junior, J., Koppe, J. & Costa, J. (2012). A Case Study Application of Linear Programming and Simulation to Mine Planning. *Journal of The Southern African Institute of Mining and Metalurgy*. 112, 477-484.
- [14]. Koesoemadinata, R.P dan Matasak: Stratigraphy and Sedimentaion of Ombilin Basin Central Sumatra (West Sumatra Province)”, *Proceed. Indonesia Petroleum Ass, Tenth Annual*